

Some New Hydrocupreidine Derivatives. Part II.

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In continuation of our previous paper (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 8, 257) in which some isoalkyl derivatives of hydrocupreidine were described, the present paper deals with the preparation and properties of the corresponding and other *n*-alkyl derivatives of the same base. The therapeutic values of these derivatives are being studied. isoButyl hydrocupreidine, which previously failed to crystallise, has now been included in the paper.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The *n*-alkyl hydrocupreidines and their hydrochlorides described below were prepared, except where otherwise mentioned, in the same way as the isoalkyl hydrocupreidines (*loc. cit.*).

n-Propylhydrocupreidine.—It is soluble in alcohol, ether and benzene. It crystallised from acetone in thin long, colourless needles, m.p. 182°. $[\alpha]_D^{25} = +206.25^\circ$ ($c=1$ in chloroform). It gives a bluish fluorescence with dilute sulphuric acid. Yield, 1.9 g. from 6 g. of hydrocupreidine. (Found: N, 8.04. $C_{22}H_{30}O_2N_2$ requires N, 7.90 per cent.).

n-Propylhydrocupreidine hydrochloride crystallised from water as long, colourless needles, m.p. 222° (decomp.). It is readily soluble in water and alcohol. $[\alpha]_D^{25} = +227.5^\circ$ ($c=1$ in water). (Found: Cl, 16.23. $C_{22}H_{30}O_2N_2$, 2HCl requires Cl, 16.60 per cent.).

n-Butylhydrocupreidine crystallised from moist acetone in colourless needles, m.p. 176°. It is soluble in absolute alcohol, ether, chloroform and benzene. It gives a bluish fluorescence with dilute sulphuric acid. $[\alpha]_D^{25} = +194.5^\circ$. ($c=1$ in chloroform). Yield, 2 g. from 6.26 g. of hydrocupreidine. (Found: N, 7.41. $C_{23}H_{32}O_2N_2$ requires N, 7.60 per cent.).

n-Butylhydrocupreidine hydrochloride crystallised from water in colourless needles. It is soluble in water and alcohol and melts with

decomposition at 226° to a dark brown liquid, $[\alpha]_D^{26} = +215^\circ$ (c=1 in water). (Found: Cl, 16·04. $C_{23}H_{32}O_2N_2 \cdot 2HCl$ requires Cl, 16·08 per cent.).

n-Amylhydrocupreidine crystallised from acetone in long colourless needles, m.p. 164°. It is soluble in absolute alcohol, ether, chloroform and benzene. It gives a bluish fluorescence with dilute sulphuric acid. $[\alpha]_D^{21} = +189\cdot25^\circ$ (c=1 in chloroform). (Found: N, 7·24.

$C_{24}H_{34}O_2N_2$ requires N, 7·33 per cent.). Yield, 3·15 g. from 6·26 g. of hydrocupreidine.

n-Amylhydrocupreidine hydrochloride crystallised from water in silky needles, m.p. 223°. It is soluble in water and alcohol. $[\alpha]_D^{26} = +212\cdot5^\circ$ (c=1 in water). (Found: Cl, 15·33. $C_{24}H_{34}O_2N_2 \cdot HCl$ requires Cl, 15·58 per cent.).

n-Heptyl hydrocupreidine crystallised from acetone in long, colourless, silky needles, m.p. 158°. It is soluble in alcohol, chloroform ether and benzene. It gives a bluish fluorescence with dilute sulphuric acid. $[\alpha]_D^{23} = +179\cdot75^\circ$ (c=1 in chloroform). (Found: N, 6·87.

$C_{26}H_{38}O_2N_2$ requires N, 6·82 per cent.). Yield, 2·5 g. from 6·26 g. of hydrocupreidine.

n-Heptylhydrocupreidine hydrochloride crystallised from water in colourless needles, m.p. 215°. It is readily soluble in absolute alcohol but less soluble in cold water. $[\alpha]_D^{26} = +195^\circ$ (c=1 in N/50 HCl).

(Found: Cl, 14·78. $C_{26}H_{38}O_2N_2 \cdot 2HCl$ requires Cl, 14·68 per cent.).

n-Octylhydrocupreidine.—As the hydrochloride of this base was very sparingly soluble in water, the method of isolation from the reaction product was slightly different. After the reaction, the mixture was cooled and poured into water when the base soon separated out on stirring as a brown powder. The mother-liquor was kept strongly alkaline by the addition of caustic soda so as to dissolve the unchanged hydrocupreidine and left overnight. It was then filtered, washed and dried. It crystallised from acetone in thin needles. It was also found that the molecular copper which was used as catalyst deposited on the walls of the reaction flask as a mirror. It seems that the copper went into combination during the reaction and was afterwards liberated as such. The base melts at 151° to a brown liquid. It is soluble in absolute alcohol, chloroform, ether and benzene. It gives a bluish fluorescence with dilute sulphuric acid.

$[\alpha]_D^{21} = +170.75^\circ$ (c=1 in chloroform). (Found : N, 6.65, $C_{27}H_{40}O_2N_2$ requires N, 6.60 per cent.). Yield, 3.85 g. from 6 g. of hydrocupreidine.

n-Octylhydrocupreidine hydrochloride crystallised from hot water in colourless, silky needles, m.p. 210° . It is soluble in hot water and alcohol and sparingly so in cold water and acetone. $[\alpha]_D^{27} = +182.5^\circ$ (c=1 in *N/10* HCl). (Found : Cl, 13.81. $C_{27}H_{40}O_2N_2, 2HCl$ requires Cl, 14.26 per cent.).

isoButyl hydrocupreidine crystallised well from acetone in colourless needles, melting at 175° . It is soluble in alcohol, ether and benzene. $[\alpha]_D^{29} = +186.7^\circ$ (c=2 in chloroform). It gives a bluish fluorescence with dilute sulphuric acid. (Found : N, 7.38. $C_{23}H_{32}O_2N_2$ requires N, 7.60 per cent.).

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